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IBERIFIER - Assessment of VLOPs (Very Large Online Platforms) and VLOSEs (Very Large Online Search Engines) Signatory Reports for the Strengthened Code of Practice on Disinformation. Report No. 2

Report

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1. Introduction

Deliverable 5.2 is the second report edited by the IBERIFIER WP5 team concerning the implementation of the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation. It provides an assessment of seven signatory reports submitted in **March 2025** to the European Code of Practice on Disinformation, a collaborative initiative involving major online platforms, advertising industry stakeholders, fact-checking networks, research institutions, and civil society organisations. The signatories evaluated in this deliverable are **Google Search, Bing, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, LinkedIn, and YouTube**.

This assessment is framed within the broader political and media landscape in the Iberian countries, particularly in light of recent political scandals and disinformation episodes that have shaped public discourse in both Portugal and Spain. These incidents have highlighted the vulnerabilities of the digital information environment and underscored the critical role of online platforms in amplifying and spreading false or misleading content. They have also reiterated the centrality of platforms in providing real-time access to news, knowledge, and connectivity on contemporary issues, underlining the key role of platform structures in **strengthening the digital public sphere**. As such, this report not only reviews the signatories' compliance with the Code but also considers the specific challenges of combating disinformation in a region marked by evolving political tensions and increased reliance on digital media, given the privileged role platforms play in addressing key social, political, and communicational issues.

The accumulation of disinformation incidents, linked not only to the political sphere but also to recent news events, such as the devastating floods in Valencia, Spain, in autumn 2024 and the total power blackout across the Iberian Peninsula in spring 2025, has heightened public sensitivity to disinformation in Spain and Portugal. In fact, according to the *Digital News Report 2025*, Portugal and Spain have become the two European Union countries where citizens express the most significant concern about disinformation.

According to the national reports of the *Digital News Report 2025* prepared with support from IBERIFIER by project partners OberCom ([Digital News Report Portugal 2025](#)) and the University of Navarra ([Digital News Report España 2025](#)), as part of the global initiative coordinated by the Reuters Institute at the University of Oxford, Portugal has emerged as the EU country where citizens are most concerned about disinformation. In Portugal, 71% of respondents expressed concern about their ability to distinguish between true and false news online, the highest percentage among EU countries. In Spain, this figure stands at 69%, placing it as the third country where people are most concerned, following the United Kingdom, which is no longer an EU member. This shared perception highlights the **growing significance of disinformation** in Iberian public discourse.

In both Iberian countries, social media plays a significant role in news consumption, although the patterns differ. In Portugal, news consumption is concentrated on a few platforms: **Facebook** remains the most used, followed by **WhatsApp and Instagram**, although **YouTube** and Instagram also have a notable presence. In contrast, in Spain, consumption is more fragmented: social media is the second most consulted news source, but no single platform clearly dominates the market. While Facebook's influence is waning, closed messaging environments like WhatsApp and the **rise of TikTok among younger users** are gaining ground, forcing media outlets to adapt their formats and strategies to a highly segmented and diverse audience. Against this backdrop, evaluating the role of digital platforms in addressing disinformation becomes a critical issue.

1.1. Objectives

1. To **evaluate a sample of the VLOPs and VLOSEs' initial compliance** and engagement with the Strengthened Code of Practice on Disinformation, focusing on their efforts to empower users via commitment 17.
2. To **recommend concrete and specific measures** for improving the implementation of the Code of Practice on Disinformation, with **a particular focus** on enhancing the effectiveness of commitment 17 related to media literacy and their localised implementation in **Portugal and Spain**.

1.2. Methodology

The evaluation presented in this report follows a standardised and collaborative methodology developed in coordination with the methodological subgroup, which includes representatives from each European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO) Hub. This subgroup met several times to discuss and harmonise the assessment approach, ensuring a consistent, transparent, and fair evaluation process across all participating hubs. A key feature of the methodology is the use of **double coding** for each assessment. This means that two independent reviewers evaluated each signatory's report, comparing interpretations and resolving discrepancies through discussion at **the first level** inside the same partner team. The second level was **intercode** among different partners. At the end, a total of fourteen coders agree on the score for the evaluation. This approach enhances the objectivity of the findings and reduces the risk of individual bias. The combination of evidence-based and qualitative assessment ensures that the report records compliance in formal terms as well as critically reflects on the **effectiveness** and **strategic relevance** of the signatories' actions in combating disinformation and fostering a more informed public. The assessment focused on three core dimensions:

- 1. Quality of the Report:** This criterion considers how clearly and systematically the signatories present their activities. It includes the organisation of the report, the clarity of language, the use of structured formats, and the overall accessibility of the information for external reviewers. A three-point Likert scale (1 = Poor, 2 = Partial, 3 = Good, 4 = Not applicable) was used, following the EDMO standardisation and guidelines (Cesarini et al., 2024; EDMO, 2024; EFCSN, 2024; Botan & Meyer, 2025).
- 2. Evidence Provided by the Signatories:** This dimension evaluates whether the described actions are supported by concrete documentation or data. Evaluators assessed the credibility, relevance, and sufficiency of the evidence presented, including links to relevant resources, examples of implemented tools, training materials, and statistical indicators. A three-point Likert scale (1 = Poor, 2 = Partial, 3 = Good, 4 = Not applicable) was used, following the EDMO standardisation and guidelines (Cesarini et al., 2024; EDMO, 2024; EFCSN, 2024; Botan & Meyer, 2025).
- 3. Impact of the Actions Implemented:** The final dimension assesses the extent to which the actions undertaken by the signatories align with the goals of **Commitment 17**, which focuses on **enhancing media literacy**. This includes the development of digital skills, the deployment of educational tools, the targeting of vulnerable populations, and broader awareness-raising strategies. The assessment also considers how well these actions are adapted to regional or national contexts, particularly relevant in the Iberian context of Spain and Portugal, where media literacy needs and disinformation dynamics may differ from other parts of Europe. A five-point Likert scale (1 = Very Poor, 2 = Poor, 3 = Fair, 4 = Good, 5 = Excellent) was used, following the EDMO standardisation and guidelines (Cesarini et al., 2024; EDMO, 2024; EFCSN, 2024; Botan & Meyer, 2025).

2. Deep assessment for the signatory Google Search

2.1. Introduction

Google Search is the most widely used search engine globally. It allows users to search for information across a wide range of content types, including websites, videos, images, maps, and news articles. The following assessment is based on the *Report by Google Ireland Limited ('Google') for the period from July 1, 2024, to December 31, 2024*, submitted in March 2025.

Table 1. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: Google Search

Signatory: Google Search	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	3- good
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	2- partial
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	4- good
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	4- good

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: 1- poor, 2- partial, 3- good.

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: 1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.

2.2. Quality of Response Assessment

Google Search's media literacy strategy is articulated through a well-structured implementation plan that integrates both technological innovation and educational outreach, with a strong emphasis on regional adaptation. The documentation outlines a multilayered approach comprising technical tools, open-source initiatives, and strategic educational collaborations. In Spain and Portugal, Google localised its efforts by deploying tools in native languages and supporting academic programs through partnerships with local institutions. Notably, features such as **About This Image**, which provides metadata, SynthID watermark detection, and contextual information to help users assess the reliability of visual content, have been expanded to 40 languages, including Spanish and Portuguese. Similarly, the tools "**About This Result**" and "**More**

About This Page" are available in these countries, enhancing users' ability to evaluate the credibility of websites encountered in search results.

From an educational standpoint, the **Super Searchers** media literacy training program, launched in Portugal in October 2024, exemplifies Google's commitment to public engagement. This initiative, implemented in collaboration with **MiudosSegurosNa.Net**, **Agarrados à Net**, and the **National Schools Coordinator**, reflects a structured, context-specific intervention. The report further details Google's collaboration with the **Raspberry Pi Foundation** and **Public Libraries 2030**, though the nature of these engagements—whether they constitute formal partnerships or are limited to one-time grants—remains unclear.

The quality of the assessment is reinforced by the inclusion of robust performance metrics across 30 European countries. These include impression proportions for content advisories linked to low relevance, rapidly changing or potentially unreliable results, as well as usage statistics for key informational features (e.g., views of the **"More About This Page"** or **"About This Result"** panel sections). While the scope and clarity of Google's technological and educational interventions are commendable, the documentation reveals a minor limitation: a lack of specificity regarding the formal structure and continuity of certain partnerships.

2.3. Verification of Reported Information

Google Search presented comprehensive quantitative data to substantiate the implementation and user engagement with its media literacy tools in Spain and Portugal. In Spain, the signature reported 4,078,508 views of the "About This Page" feature, 58,946,872 views of the **Source** panel, 57,742,752 views of the **"Your Search" and this result** section, and 49,286,500 views of the **Personalisation** panel. Comparable figures in Portugal included 754,972 views for **About This Page**, 11,476,200 views for the **Source** panel, 11,293,812 views for **Your Search and this result**, and 9,653,604 for **Personalisation**. These data demonstrate a significant level of public interaction with Google's credibility-assessment tools in both countries.

In addition to usage statistics, Google reported estimated impression proportions for content advisories in three categories: low-relevance results (Portugal: 0.007%, Spain: 0.006%), rapidly changing results (Portugal: 0.00006%, Spain: 0.00008%), and potentially unreliable result sets (Portugal: 0.0000052%, Spain: 0.000007%). These indicators suggest targeted deployment of advisories in response to content quality, reinforcing the platform's commitment to information reliability.

The report further enhances its transparency by offering detailed metrics across 30 European countries and by providing hyperlinks to supplementary resources, including

explanatory materials related to the educational programs deployed. This integrated approach, combining technical metrics, geographic disaggregation, and accessible contextual materials, strengthens the evaluation of the initiative's scope and effectiveness without compromising clarity or conciseness.

2.4. Evaluation of Actions Taken

Google Search's contribution to user awareness and media literacy is built upon a strategic combination of **visibility** (via impression rates), **accessibility** (through extensive language support), and **functional features** (such as deep linking, source transparency, and metadata context). Together, these components are designed to empower users to engage critically with digital content and navigate the information ecosystem more effectively.

In **Portugal**, the online search demonstrated tangible impact through its **Super Searchers** program, which trained **490 educators across 16 sessions**, reaching an estimated **14,700 students** in its initial phase. This initiative reflects a dual strategy of tool deployment and capacity-building within local educational systems. The Google program was developed and supported by the National Schools Coordinator in collaboration with local NGOs (*MiudosSegurosNa.Net* and *Agarrados à Net*), ensuring curricular alignment and institutional adoption.

In **Spain**, the impact is reflected in extremely high engagement metrics. Media literacy features, such as "**About This Result**" and "**About This Image**," are available in Spanish, enhancing user comprehension and fostering trust during the information retrieval process. Usage data indicates **tens of millions of interactions**, highlighting a significant level of user engagement.

Despite these strengths, some limitations remain. Although tool usage figures are high in absolute terms, the **relative percentage of users engaging with these features remains low**, consistent with trends observed in other countries. Moreover, **no equivalent educational initiative** to the Portuguese *Super Searchers* program has been launched in Spain, and **initiatives such as the Raspberry Pi Foundation collaboration lack direct national implementation** in the Iberian context. While partnerships are highlighted, the depth and continuity of these collaborations, particularly outside of Portugal, remain insufficiently detailed.

Google Search's efforts nonetheless reflect a clear and ongoing commitment to **technical innovation and advancing media literacy**. Notable examples include:

1. Deployment of **SynthID text watermarking** via its Responsible Generative AI Toolkit.

2. Expansion of the *About This Image* feature to **40 new languages** and integration with **Google Lens**.
3. Implementation of the **C2PA Content Credentials standard** to enhance authenticity verification.
Iterative enhancements to features such as *About This Result* and *More About This Page*, aimed at improving **information quality and transparency**.
4. Introduction of **Content Advisory Notices**, which alert users when information is limited or evolving rapidly—an intervention designed specifically to address data voids and reduce misinformation exposure.

Furthermore, Google has **actively consulted and partnered with media literacy experts**, including:

1. Co-designing tools with information literacy specialists.
2. Collaborating with **Public Libraries 2030** and local NGOs in Portugal.
3. Integrating its educational content with national curricula through coordination with the **Portuguese National Schools Coordinator**.
4. In summary, while the reach and technical sophistication of Google Search's media literacy tools are notable, their **effectiveness at a population scale** remains constrained by relatively low user engagement rates and uneven geographic implementation. Nonetheless, the **breadth, measurability, and transparency** of the interventions provide a strong foundation for scalable impact.

2.5. Recommendations/need for improvement

1. The implementation of the **educational programme in Spain** (similar to the Portuguese one) could improve the local impact of user empowerment strategies.
2. Consider the potential positive impact of promoting Google Search tools, such as '**About This Result**' and '**More About This Page**,' through marketing strategies, to enhance their reach in quantitative terms.

3. Deep assessment for the signatory YouTube

3.1. Introduction

YouTube is a global online platform designed for sharing, uploading, and viewing videos. Owned by Google, it hosts a vast and diverse range of content, including music videos, tutorials, documentaries, vlogs, educational materials, and entertainment. The following assessment is based on the *Report by Google Ireland Limited ('Google') for the period from July 1, 2024, to December 31, 2024*, and was submitted in March 2025.

Table 2. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: YouTube

Signatory: YouTube	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	1- poor
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	1- poor
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	2- poor
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	2- poor

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: 1- poor, 2- partial, 3- good.

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: 1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.

3.2. Quality of Response Assessment

YouTube reports some initiatives to address misinformation and promote media literacy, including **Information Panels**, which provide contextual and verified information alongside videos to help users identify and understand misinformation, **and the Hit Pause campaign**, which is a series of videos encouraging users to pause and reflect before sharing content, aiming to reduce the spread of misinformation.

However, the reporting lacks consistent details about the impact or effectiveness of these initiatives. The description of grants and projects supported under Commitment 17 does not clarify their expected outcomes.

3.3. Verification of Reported Information

The data provided by the signatory is insufficient to verify the impact of YouTube's initiatives properly.

No evidence is presented to demonstrate whether the Information Panels are consistently linked to all relevant videos or only to those suspected of containing misinformation. Also, there is a noticeable disparity in the reach of Information Panels between Spain and Portugal, with Portugal receiving significantly fewer impressions. The reasons for this discrepancy are unclear, and no explanation is provided. Metrics primarily focus on impressions, without additional indicators such as click-through rates or engagement data that would enable a more accurate assessment of their effectiveness.

Similarly, no detailed data is given on user interaction with the Hit Pause campaign, despite YouTube's ability to provide in-depth analytics for its content channels. Although the impressions appear to be similar in Spain and Portugal, in proportion to the internet user base in both countries, deeper insights are needed, as impressions are a **poor key performance indicator (KPI)** on their own.

Overall, the data lacks granularity and depth, making a robust evaluation impossible.

3.4. Evaluation of Actions Taken

YouTube's Information Panels and Hit Pause campaign appear to have some reach, but the lack of detailed metrics, beyond impressions, **limits assessment of their actual impact.**

There is no specific information available about the effects of these initiatives in Spain and Portugal. The significant differences in impressions between these countries raise questions that remain unanswered.

Moreover, the signatory does not provide evidence of active monitoring or evaluation to ensure that Information Panels are correctly displayed in all relevant videos. The absence of engagement metrics such as click-through rates or average viewing times further restricts impact analysis.

There is no ongoing direct collaboration between YouTube and national media literacy hubs. The signatory is encouraged to increase the number of organisations and experts it consults, as there are many entities specialising in different aspects of media and literacy skills. A wide range of stakeholders are present in Spain and Portugal, and existing research indicates that the Iberian context presents distinct challenges. These issues could be more effectively addressed through active engagement with experts who possess in-depth knowledge of the local socio-political and media environments.

3.5. Recommendations/need for improvement

Reporting may be substantially improved by the signatory, adding more qualitative and quantitative elements to support the signatory's claims. Thus, the overall negative evaluation is mainly related to the level of detail in reporting rather than the scope and nature of the initiatives promoted by the signatory. Elements to include in future reporting exercises:

1. Consistent data regarding the commitment to Article 17 in Spain and Portugal, specifically. It is not possible to assess the impact of the signatory's endeavours in Iberian countries, specifically, as well as the importance of promoting said endeavours in Spanish and Portuguese.
2. Data is insufficient. Signatory relies heavily on impressions as a metric for the success of its initiatives. Impressions are an interesting indicator, but they are less significant compared to others, such as click-through rates, which measure users' commitment to the initiatives promoted by the signatory. This is particularly relevant for this particular signatory, as efficient and unequivocal indicators and metrics are at the core of their digital infrastructure and products.
3. **Collaboration-wise**, the reporting is lacklustre in terms of the partnerships established by the signatory. This is not necessarily due to the absence of these collaborations, but instead to the lack of detail in reporting, as the signatory is known for its extensive network of projects in Europe.

4. Deep assessment for the signatory LinkedIn

4.1. Introduction

LinkedIn is a professional networking platform owned by Microsoft. It is used to connect with colleagues, find job opportunities, and share industry-related content. It also enables companies and professionals to showcase their expertise and establish a robust online presence. In this report, we evaluated the most helpful resources on misinformation from July 1, 2024, to December 31, 2024, based on data from LinkedIn's Help Center.

Table 3. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: LinkedIn

Signatory: LinkedIn	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	1- poor
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	1- poor
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	1- very poor
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	1- very poor

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: 1- poor, 2- partial, 3- good.

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: 1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.

4.2. Quality of Response Assessment

The signature outlines a general commitment to combating misinformation through content moderation policies, curated news content by editors, and educational resources available via its **Help Center**. However, it did not include any new tools, policies, or activities introduced in 2024.

The actions listed represent passive and indirect forms of media literacy. Some examples include automated tools to remove content that violates LinkedIn's misinformation policies, a specific protocol for users to report inappropriate content, curated information by a global team of editors, and collaborations with organisations like **Verified** or **The**

Trust Project. These initiatives, while relevant, lack interactive features or locally adapted approaches that could strengthen users' media literacy in more active ways.

4.3. Verification of Reported Information

The only measurable data point provided by LinkedIn is the number of visits to a Help Center article on how to detect and combat misinformation on LinkedIn, which compiles helpful third-party resources to identify misinformation. This is inadequate as evidence of engagement, impact, or learning outcomes.

Regarding platform engagement metrics related to media literacy tools, the available data is notably limited, including for the Iberian countries. According to the figures reported, Spain recorded 109 visits to the **Help Center** article mentioned before, while Portugal accounted for only 32 visits to relevant features or content during the reporting period. However, no additional data was provided by the signatory regarding user engagement with educational content or the effectiveness of curated news coverage. The information is insufficient to evaluate the actual efficacy of these initiatives.

LinkedIn neither tracked engagement in the collaborative literacy campaigns nor provided evidence of improvements in media literacy.

4.4. Evaluation of Actions Taken

LinkedIn's efforts are limited in both scope and depth. While the platform contributes to the Code by curating trustworthy content and pointing users to external educational initiatives, these actions remain passive. There is no evidence of mechanisms to measure user comprehension or behavioural change, and no locally adapted strategies were implemented for Spain or Portugal.

The only action accompanied by quantitative data, the number of visits to a Help Center article on misinformation, reveals a low impact among users, with fewer than 1,000 visits in any given country during the reported period. In Spain and Portugal, the metrics are exceptionally modest: 109 and 32 visits, respectively. No other information, such as 'average reading time', is provided, so it is not possible to quantify the impact of this action (some views can be '**clicks by accident**', for example). No data is provided for the other actions listed, so it is not possible to assess their impact.

Although the signatory mentions collaborations with external organisations and describes their tools in detail, LinkedIn has not developed other interactive actions to complement these efforts. The report did not indicate cooperation with national media literacy hubs or local institutions in Spain or Portugal. LinkedIn also did not involve EU-level bodies, such

as the **European Data Protection Supervisor** (EDPS) or the **European Data Protection Board** (EDPB), in its strategy.

As mentioned earlier, the report lacks sufficient data on the impact of the actions, making it difficult to assess their effectiveness. The only action that presents quantitative data indicates that it has not had a significant impact at the global level.

4.5. Recommendations/need for improvement

1. To more effectively evaluate the impact of media literacy initiatives, signatories should include additional engagement metrics, such as interaction rates, as well as information on any follow-up actions taken.
2. Given the very low engagement metrics in Spain and Portugal, it is recommended that media literacy content be promoted more proactively in these markets.
3. Strengthen or initiate collaborations with EU and national media literacy hubs, including those active in Spain and Portugal, to enhance local relevance and visibility.

5. Deep assessment for the signatory Bing

5.1. Introduction

Bing is a web search engine owned and operated by Microsoft. It enables users to search for information across various websites, images, videos, maps, and news sources. The following assessment is based on the *Microsoft (Bing) Report for the period from July 1, 2024, to December 31, 2024*.

Table 4. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: Bing Search

Signatory: Bing	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	3- good
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	2- partial
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	4- good
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	4- good

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: 1- poor, 2- partial, 3- good.

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: 1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.

5.1. Quality of Response Assessment

Bing has implemented several measures to enhance users' media literacy during their interaction with the search engine. These include features such as **Knowledge Cards**, **Transparency Hubs**, and **Public Service Announcements**.

Additionally, the platform highlights efforts to provide authoritative information on elections, display AI-generated content disclaimers, and deliver training sessions under the Tech Accord initiative.

These initiatives reflect the overall commitment to support informed digital participation.

5.2. Verification of Reported Information

Bing provides impression metrics for both Transparency hubs and Public Service Announcements, as well as engagement metrics related to Knowledge Cards. This level of reporting is adequate, although it could be better if more detailed metrics were available, such as click-through rates or user interaction time.

The signatory also reports having developed training sessions for political parties, candidates, and election officials to enhance their understanding of deepfakes and how to protect against their use in elections. However, no specific data is available concerning user engagement with authoritative election information or AI disclaimers.

5.3. Evaluation of Actions Taken

Bing reports some actions to address misinformation and enhance media literacy. Regarding the **Knowledge Cards**, which provide quick definitions and contextual information within search results, they represent a valuable and accessible measure of media literacy for Bing users. However, the content of these cards is mainly based on Wikipedia, which may not be considered a sufficiently authoritative source. Despite this, the data provided on impressions suggests a high level of user adoption.

The Transparency Hubs represent another effort to give users access to verified and trustworthy information. However, the signatory does not provide significant metrics to assess the effectiveness of this measure. It only reports the number of transparency hubs implemented, but there is no data related to the reach or engagement with this tool.

Bing also implemented **Public Service Announcements**, which deliver curated information to users. As in the case of the Knowledge Cards, the number of impressions provided also suggests good adoption of the tool.

Regarding the Tech Accord, which includes training sessions on deepfakes for political parties and candidates, only 50 sessions were conducted across EEA countries, reaching approximately 500 participants, a relatively small number considering the potential audience.

The signatory mentions ongoing collaborations with journalists, organisations and companies such as OpenAI. However, there is no evidence of direct cooperation between the signatory and national media literacy hubs.

5.4. Recommendations/need for improvement

1. Increase transparency by providing more detailed engagement metrics for all media literacy tools.
2. Diversify sources beyond **Wikipedia for Knowledge Cards** to enhance authority and reliability.
3. Provide data on the reach and user interaction with Transparency Hubs to better assess impact.
4. Expand Tech Accord training sessions to reach a broader audience across EEA countries.
5. Strengthen collaboration with **national media literacy hubs** and local organisations for tailored outreach.

6. Deep assessment for the signatory TikTok

6.1. Introduction

TikTok is a platform for creating and watching short videos. It is widely used for entertainment, trends, and creative expression, and increasingly serves as a way to search for and discover information through visual content. The following assessment is based on the *TikTok Report for the period from July 1, 2024, to December 31, 2024*.

Table 5. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: TikTok

Signatory: TikTok	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	3- good
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	1- poor
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	2- poor
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	2- poor

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: 1- poor, 2- partial, 3- good.

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: 1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.

6.2. Quality of Response Assessment

The signatory indicates that it conducted eleven general media literacy and critical thinking **skills campaigns** in collaboration with fact-checkers and media literacy partners (in Portugal Poligrafo collaborates), fourteen temporary media literacy and **electoral integrity campaigns** before regional elections (not reported in Spain or Portugal, although there were no elections) and 9 Election Speaker Series sessions (not reported in Spain or Portugal).

The signatory activated four temporary in-app natural disaster search guides (related to wildfires in Portugal and floods in Spain) and continued with previously implemented in-app functionalities (video tags, search interventions, public service announcement,

unverified content tag and in-app information centres) in the context of elections, conflicts, health and environmental issues.

Regarding climate content, collaboration with **Verified for Climate** continues to combat misinformation and disinformation, with TikTok creators developing educational content (this initiative also includes Spain). Regarding health information, in collaboration with the WHO, they support the Fides network for mental well-being awareness and literacy.

The signatory continues to develop its policies for labelling state-affiliated media in collaboration with 'external experts' (this action includes Spain and Portugal), which involves restricting access to content from the entities sanctioned by the EU in 2024.

They continue to improve the labelling of AI-generated content, including media literacy campaigns for creators, as well as the **Safety Center and Transparency Center**, with specific sections addressing harmful misinformation and the European Elections Integrity Hub (currently unavailable).

6.3. Verification of Reported Information

The signatory reports some in-app interventions: state-controlled media label, video notice tag (Holocaust misinformation/denial; mpox; elections), search interventions (Holocaust misinformation/denial; mpox; climate change; elections), public service announcements (Holocaust misinformation/denial; mpox); these data are limited to impressions, clicks and click-through rates.

Data is included for general media literacy and critical thinking skills campaigns, concerning Portugal (in collaboration with **Polígrafo**) and Spain (**Maldita**); these campaigns are not clearly defined.

The quantitative responses focus on measuring the Safety Center, specifically the number of impressions, clicks, and click-through rates of video notice tags, search interventions, and public service announcements related to campaigns in each country. No data is provided for other actions, such as those related to specific elections, the war in Ukraine, the Israel-Hamas conflict, or climate literacy.

It would be interesting to know the impact of the actions taken in response to the **Portuguese wildfires and Spanish floods**, for which no data are available. It should also be noted that quantitative data (impressions, clicks, click-through rate) are insufficient to assess effectiveness.

6.4. Evaluation of Actions Taken

It is difficult to assess the effectiveness of each action because data is missing for most actions. Although the signatory reflects a variety of activities, tools and collaborations, the available data show a limited impact (click-through rate is very low, which represents that very few people interact with these functionalities). The data available for Spain and Portugal are equally limited, as they refer to only a few interventions.

The available data refer to actions in specific thematic topics that, during the reporting period, have low relevance. Therefore, it is difficult to assess their impact (e.g., mpox).

The report mentions **international collaboration** with partners like Fact-checking Australian Associated Press (AAP), Agence France-Presse (AFP), Animal Político, Code for Africa, Deutsche Presse-Agentur, Estadão Verifica, Facta, Lead Stories, Logically, Newschecker, Newtral, PolitiFact, Reuters, Science Feedback, and Teyit. Additionally, we partner with the National Association for Media Literacy Education (NAMLE) for media literacy initiatives. Nevertheless, there is no evidence showing specific actions of collaboration with any of them.

The signatory explains the methodology for measuring data. Then, it presents the data for various activities across 30 European countries. Nevertheless, quantitative data (such as the number of impressions, clicks, and click-through rate) are very limited in assessing the effectiveness of tools, activities, and partnerships.

In addition to the weaknesses identified in Sections 6.3 and 6.4 (there are actions without reported data), the data available for Spain and Portugal reflect a low impact (click-through rate $\leq 1.83\%$).

Although there is no explicit reference to the Iberifier hub, partnerships are identified with Polígrafo in Portugal and Maldita in Spain, both of which are Iberifier partners.

6.5. Recommendations/need for improvement

1. Although there is a good performance in the response to commitment 17, it is recommended to provide more specific information on general media literacy and critical thinking skills campaigns, concerning Portugal (**in collaboration with Polígrafo) and Spain (Maldita).**
2. It would be recommended to provide data on the impact of specific actions (for example, the Portuguese wildfires and Spanish floods during this period).
3. In general terms, the quantitative data reported (**impressions, clicks, click-through rate**) are insufficient to assess effectiveness.
4. Finally, it would be recommended to provide data on all the actions developed for a fairer assessment, rather than limiting them to in-app and search interventions and public service announcements.

7. Deep assessment for the signatory Facebook

7.1. Introducción

Facebook is a social media platform owned by Meta. It allows users to connect, share content, join groups, and discover information through posts, pages, and personalised recommendations. The following assessment is based on the *Facebook Report for the period from July 1, 2024, to December 31, 2024*.

Table 7. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: Facebook

Signatory: Instagram	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	2- partial
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	1- poor
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	2- poor
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	2- poor

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: 1- poor, 2- partial, 3- good.

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: 1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.

7.1. Quality of Response Assessment

Meta has presented a comprehensive and diverse strategy to combat misinformation and promote digital literacy across the European Union, aligning with the objectives outlined in Commitment 17.

This strategy integrates **user-facing tools**, such as notification screens for outdated articles, verified account badges, and warning screens, with wider awareness campaigns addressing issues like fraud, scams, and election integrity. The company has also introduced inclusive measures, including a media literacy initiative in collaboration with the **European Disability Forum (EDF)** aimed at promoting accessible elections. A youth-targeted campaign is scheduled for early 2025 in Spain and four additional EU countries. Furthermore, Meta has implemented a range of media literacy initiatives

focused on themes such as generative AI, youth engagement, and the European Union elections. The signature has also launched a global **anti-fraud and anti-scam campaign** that includes several EU countries (notably excluding Portugal).

Additionally, Meta has deployed content tagging via fact-checking mechanisms. It has also developed third-party literacy partnerships in six EU member states. However, the specific national and civil society partners involved in Spain and Portugal were not disclosed by the signature.

Despite the breadth of these activities, several limitations persist. There **is little publicly available information on the country-specific deployment of tools like warning screens and verification features**, which appear to operate platform-wide rather than being tailored or localised to the contexts of Spain or Portugal.

Moreover, reviewers did not identify new implementation measures for Portugal. The current Very Large Online Platform (VLOP) reporting remains primarily descriptive and lacks sufficient data to assess the actual impact of these interventions at the national level. While Meta's approach is comprehensive in design, the absence of impact evaluation limits its demonstrable effectiveness.

Nonetheless, a particularly noteworthy and commendable development is Meta's proactive decision to seek an independent assessment report. This action demonstrates a significant commitment to transparency, accountability, and continuous improvement, setting a positive precedent for evaluating the efficacy of digital platform interventions within the framework of the **Digital Services Act**.

7.2. Verification of Reported Information

Meta provided quantitative data for some **EU-wide campaigns**, especially the Fraud and Scams initiative. Still, the signature failed to deliver the SLI 17.1.1 metrics for tools (i.e., no impressions, interactions, or usage by country).

Regarding Spain-specific data, included in the **Fraud and Scams campaign**, which ran from Nov 11 to Dec 31, 2024, on Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp.

No user interaction numbers are provided for Spain or Portugal in the SLI table (all entries show "0").

Limitations:

Meta did not provide any disaggregated engagement data for Portugal or Spain at the national level.

Campaign reach and impressions were only broken down for France and Ireland.

Without tool usage data or user behaviour indicators, it is not easy to measure actual engagement or impact.

They offer supporting data for some activities:

1) Election literacy campaign (France): Reach: 2.1 million people; Impressions: 10.6 million

2) Irish Elections: On channels outside Meta-owned platforms, the campaign reached 436.5K users.

3) Fraud & Scams: The campaign reached 23.8 million users, generating 460 million impressions. Warning screens – There is no data available to demonstrate the effectiveness of this resource in reducing users' exposure to sensitive content. Does it reduce the circulation, reach and impact of said content? (Impact of flagged vs non-flagged content). We are particularly interested in data related to Spain and Portugal.

Verified badges – How well does the verification program perform, in terms of the diversity and scope of the pages/actors it covers? Particular attention is given to reaching out to key actors, such as journalists. **Local and regional press outlets?** Despite the valid mention of fraud and scams, there is reason to believe that verification systems may impact the relationship between users and disinformation, particularly about the perceived trustworthiness of content.

Notification screens on outdated articles - Would it be possible to show the effectiveness of this resource in reducing the circulation of older or out-of-context information? Does it reduce its circulation, reach and impact? We're particularly interested in data related to Spain and Portugal, and this may be key during electoral periods, for instance.

7.3. Evaluation of Actions Taken

Meta's campaigns, particularly the Fraud & Scams and upcoming Youth campaigns, help raise awareness and provide context for users. However, a lack of data on user engagement and limited visibility on outcomes specific to Spain and Portugal undermines effectiveness.

Tools like outdated article notifications or verified badges support media literacy passively, but are not integrated with impact measurement.

The campaigns appear centralised and not adapted to local media literacy needs.

Nevertheless, the combination of technical interventions and awareness campaigns yields a moderate impact score for Meta.

Meta has deployed a wide range of tools that support media literacy by informing users about the credibility of content (e.g., verified badges and warnings for outdated articles). Campaigns focused on fraud and digital literacy reached a broad audience. However, the lack of localised or interactive interventions limits their transformative potential in Iberian contexts. Warning screens (Poor); Verified badges (Poor); Notification screens on outdated articles (Poor); National elections (Poor); Frauds and scams (Poor).

For the reasons listed above (poor reporting and metrics), it is not possible to assess the effectiveness of the initiative. Additionally, there is no relevant information regarding the specific impact in Spain and Portugal. Impressions are an insufficient KPI in this instance. There appears to be some reach for these initiatives, but the reported data lacks granularity, both between and within countries.

Tools provide relevant context and support the safe navigation of information.

The **Fraud & Scams** campaign reached tens of millions of users across the EU, but no data was shared for Iberian countries.

The **Youth campaign in Spain**, although post-reporting period, indicates a forward-looking national strategy.

No evidence of local adaptation or evaluation of behavioural impact on users in Spain or Portugal. For the reasons listed above, our ability to assess the effects of tools, activities and partnerships is limited.

Meta reports ongoing collaboration with a wide range of media literacy experts and international institutions (e.g., EAVI, UNESCO, Yale, Harvard). It also participates in the EU Digital Citizenship Working Group.

However, no specific collaborations with national media literacy hubs, educational institutions, or civil society in Spain or Portugal were reported.

Involvement with **EDMO, ERGA's Media Literacy Action Group**, or national experts was not mentioned. A more comprehensive list of partnerships is needed, namely by country.

7.4. Recommendations/need for improvement

1. It is recommended that the available qualitative data be expanded to allow for a more complete and comprehensive evaluation of effectiveness.
2. To provide more specific information and data on the campaigns and actions carried out in Spain and Portugal, allowing for a comparison with the rest of the countries.
3. The overall quality of reporting is substantially dependent on the availability of better engagement metrics and indicators, such as click-through rates.
4. Facebook should increase the number of organisations and experts it consults with, as there is a vast number of organisations specialising in different facets of media and literacy skills. There are numerous partners to consider in Spain and Portugal, and research has shown that specific issues arise in the Iberian countries, which could be actively mitigated by reaching out to experts knowledgeable about the local reality.

8. Deep assessment for the signatory Instagram

8.1. Introduction

Instagram is a social media platform owned by Meta Platforms, Inc. It focuses on sharing photos, videos, and stories, and is also used to explore trends, follow interests, and discover content through hashtags and the search function. The following assessment is based on the *Instagram Report for the period from July 1, 2024, to December 31, 2024*.

Table 7. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: Instagram

Signatory: Instagram	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	1- poor
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	1- poor
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	1- very poor
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	1- very poor

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: 1- poor, 2- partial, 3- good.

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: 1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.

8.1. Quality of Response Assessment

Meta has documented several Instagram-related actions that align with Commitment 17. These include **warning screens on sensitive content** to help users assess posts before engaging, verified badges to distinguish authentic from impersonated accounts, and Awareness-raising campaigns (e.g., Fraud and Scams) that ran on Instagram in Spain and other EU markets.

A Youth-focused campaign was launched in January 2025, including Spain, although it falls outside the reporting window.

Meta also partnered with expert organisations such as the European Disability Forum to promote accessible elections and reported active involvement in the EU Digital Citizenship working group.

Limitations:

There is no specific mention of tools or campaigns uniquely tailored to Portugal.

Tools and campaigns are generalised across Meta platforms; Instagram-specific strategies could be better disaggregated. They mention four actions:

- 1) Election literacy campaign (France)
- 2) Fraud and scam campaign (EU): Spain is listed as one of the countries where the action took place; Portugal is not.
- 3) 3rd-party literacy partnerships (6 countries): **National and Civil Society Partners** not disclosed, not in Spain or Portugal.
- 4) Content labelled via fact-checking

Moreover, two disclosed partnerships:

- 1) European Fact-Checking Standards Network (EFCSN) - For the Election Literacy Campaign in France
- 2) European Disability Forum (EDF) - For the Election literacy campaign in France. Instagram's report offers shared information with Facebook. It refers to French and Irish electorate campaigns, but is a "Meta" information more than an Instagram information.

8.2. Verification of Reported Information

The signature did not report Member State-level engagement metrics for Instagram tools (warning screens, verified badges), and the official SLI 17.1.1 section states that there were "0" impressions or interactions for Spain and Portugal.

Campaign Evidence:

The **Fraud and Scams campaign** ran on Instagram in Spain, but no Spain-specific metrics (e.g., reach, impressions) were provided.

The French election campaign on Instagram generated 10.6 million impressions, but no equivalent data was shared for Spain or Portugal.

For Portugal, there were no reported campaigns or tool usage metrics at all.

In conclusion, the absence of national-level metrics severely limits the ability to assess performance in Iberian countries. They only offer supporting data for two activities:

1) Election literacy campaign (France): Reach: 2.1 million people; Impressions: 10.6 million

2) Content labelled via fact-checking: Over 1 million pieces of content had their distribution reduced due to fact-checking reviews (Instagram used 43,000+ distinct fact-checking articles in the EU). In terms of metrics, the report only offers data from the French campaign, which reached 2.1 million users, generating 10.6 million impressions. Many relevant partners are involved, but the signature report did not describe the terms under which these collaborations operate. No metrics for those collaborations. Partners include various government bodies (such as ministries of education and media regulators), our global network of third-party fact checkers, parent-teacher associations, the **European Association for Viewers Interests (EAVI)**, the UNESCO Institute for Information Technologies in Education (UNESCO IITE), Yale University, Harvard University, the **Micro: bit Educational Foundation**, and many more.

Meta also belongs to the **Steering Committee of the EU Digital Citizenship working group**.

8.3. Evaluation of Actions Taken

The tools and campaigns implemented by Instagram are relevant, but their impact remains unproven due to:

Lack of localisation or country-level focus (especially in Portugal).

There is no tracking of learning outcomes, behavioural change, or comprehension impact among Instagram users.

Reliance on passive features (e.g., content warnings, badges), with no evidence of user empowerment or critical thinking improvement.

The upcoming **Youth campaign** in Spain shows promise, but falls outside the evaluation period. Instagram's report offers shared information with Facebook. It refers to French and Irish electorate campaigns, but is a "Meta" information more than an Instagram information. Regarding the effectiveness rate, it is difficult to determine, considering the data provided by Instagram.

The tools deployed (e.g. warning screens, verified badges) are helpful but basic. The signature run in Spain's Fraud and Scams campaign did not include localised follow-up or measurement, and no initiatives were reported for Portugal. It is not possible to discuss this based on the data provided by Instagram.

There was no reported engagement in Spain or Portugal (0 impressions reported).

Campaigns were largely EU-focused rather than tailored to national contexts.

There is minimal evidence of partnerships or activities tailored to Iberian audiences.

The lack of disaggregated metrics hinders any meaningful evaluation of reach or success.

The signature collaborates with a range of international partners (e.g., EAVI, UNESCO IITE, Yale) and participates in the EU Digital Citizenship Working Group. However:

No specific partnerships with national experts or media literacy hubs in Spain or Portugal were reported by the signature.

No mention of engagement with EDMO, ERGA, or local NGOs relevant to media literacy in the Iberian context. The only media literacy-related action that explicitly included Spain was the Fraud and Scam Awareness Campaign. However, no supporting data, such as reach, impressions, or engagement metrics, was provided to assess its impact.

Additionally, Spain and Portugal may have indirectly benefited from the fact-checking initiative on Instagram, where over 1 million pieces of content were labelled or had their distribution reduced across the EU. Nevertheless, as with the **fraud campaign**, no country-specific metrics were disclosed, making it impossible to evaluate the precise impact in either country.

8.4. Recommendations/need for improvement

To strengthen its contribution under Commitment 17, Instagram could:

1. Localise actions and metrics, particularly for underrepresented Member States like Portugal or Spain.
2. Establish and report on local partnerships with media literacy organisations, fact-checkers, educators, and NGOs in Spain and Portugal.

9. Conclusions

Across the seven signatories assessed (**Google Search, YouTube, LinkedIn, Bing, TikTok, Facebook, and Instagram**), marked differences emerged in the quality of responses, verification of reported information, and evaluation of actions taken under Commitment 17. In terms of **Quality of Response Assessment**, Google Search and Bing provided the most structured and articulated reports, with well-documented initiatives and regional adaptations, particularly for the Iberian context. In contrast, platforms like Instagram, YouTube, and LinkedIn submitted less detailed and often fragmented narratives, offering minimal localisation or country-specific strategies for Spain and Portugal.

Regarding **the Verification of Reported Information**, only Google Search presented robust supporting data, including disaggregated usage statistics and performance indicators. In contrast, most other platforms, particularly Instagram, LinkedIn, and TikTok, relied heavily on generic impression data without providing engagement metrics or qualitative indicators, thereby limiting the capacity for external verification.

In the **Evaluation of Actions Taken**, Google and Bing again stood out for implementing tangible and partially measurable initiatives. In contrast, Meta's platforms (Facebook and Instagram), along with YouTube and TikTok, adopted generalised EU-wide approaches that lacked national specificity and did not demonstrate clear behavioural impact or media literacy outcomes in the Iberian countries. Overall, the assessment reveals an uneven implementation landscape, with only a minority of signatories meeting the necessary standards of transparency, localisation, and effectiveness required for rigorous monitoring under Commitment 17.

In monitoring Commitment 17, it is essential to consider its alignment with broader policy frameworks such as the European Commission's initiatives in media literacy, notably the new *Digital Education Action Plan*. Within this context, the Signatories have committed to continuing and strengthening their efforts in the areas of media literacy and critical thinking, with a particular focus on the inclusion of vulnerable groups. In addition, Code's Taskforce must be focused on tangible, country-specific actions that reflect the diversity of media ecosystems and societal needs across Member States. Therefore, **future signatory efforts should prioritise geographic inclusivity**, contextual sensitivity, and actionable metrics, with a stronger emphasis on collaboration with local actors and transparency in reporting.

In light of the above, the overall quality and **completeness of the signatory reports remain limited**, particularly in terms of their responsiveness to the specific socio-cultural and informational contexts of Spain and Portugal. While some platforms demonstrate a broad and methodologically diverse set of initiatives under Commitment 17, the lack of disaggregated data, measurable outcomes, and localised actions undermines their transparency and evaluability. The signature reports often reflect a pan-European logic, with tools and campaigns designed for continental reach but with minimal adaptation to the distinct media environments of Iberian countries. Given IBERIFIER's role as a regional observatory tasked with monitoring digital media and platform accountability, the exclusion or marginal treatment of Spain and Portugal in both strategic planning and reporting is especially concerning. Concrete, country-specific initiatives and partnerships are necessary to ensure that the objectives of the Code of Practice are met in practice, not only in principle.

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IBERIFIER – Iberian Digital Media Observatory

IBERIFIER is a digital media observatory in Spain and Portugal funded by the European Commission, linked to the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO). It comprises thirteen universities, five fact-checking organisations and news agencies, and five multidisciplinary research centres.

Its primary mission is to analyse the Iberian digital media ecosystem and address the issue of misinformation. To do this, it focuses its research on five lines of work:

1. Research on the characteristics and trends of the Iberian digital media ecosystem.
2. Development of computational technologies for the early detection of misinformation.
3. Fact-checking of misinformation in the Iberian territory.
4. Strategic reports on threats of disinformation, both for public knowledge and for the authorities of Spain and Portugal.
5. Promotion of media literacy initiatives, targeting journalists and informants, young people, and society as a whole.

For more information, please visit the project website at iberifier.eu

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